

ANALYSIS OF ERGONOMIC RISK ASSESSMENT OF EMPLOYEES IN THE PAN COATING DIVISION (SUGAR COATING) AT PT. X

ANALISIS PENILAIAN TINGKAT RISIKO ERGONOMI PADA PEGAWAI DIVISI COATING PAN (PELAPISAN GULA) PADA PRODUKSI COKELAT MESES PT. X

Yukeu Dwi Hasyti ¹, and Indah Rachmatiah Siti Salami ²

¹ Master Program in Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Bandung Institute of Technology

² Environmental Management Technology Expertise Group, Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Bandung Institute of Technology
ganesha 10 Bandung 40132, Indonesia

Abstract. Ergonomics has a close relationship with human functional characteristics, such as sensory ability, response, memory, optimum position of the hands and feet. The pan coating division itself is one of the production processes in chocolate meses products. Employees in the coating pan division work in a standing position with working hours of 8 hours/day with 6 (six) days in 1 (one) week. Awkward posture movements are a risk factor for disorders, diseases, or injuries to the musculoskeletal system. Fatigue is the body's protective mechanism so that the body avoids further damage, resulting in recovery. All types of work, both formal and informal, lead to job burnout, by reducing performance and increasing work errors. Ergonomics factors are not good, physical environment, respondent's physical condition, fatigue and *musculoskeletal disorders* (MSDs) which affect the risk of ergonomics in coating pan employees. The characteristics of the respondents, namely age, weight and height, have a strong relationship with work fatigue and *Musculoskeletal Disorders* (MSDs)/muscle fatigue. Ergonomics risk level assessment uses the *Rapid Upper Limb Assessment* (RULA) method and the Nordic Body Map (NBM). For fatigue, fill out the *Subjective Symptom* (SST) questionnaire where the questionnaire contains 30 questions regarding symptoms of work fatigue. The purpose of this research is to find out the problems and risk levels of ergonomics in the coating pan (sugar coating) work on PT. X. Knowing the effect of the physical environment, individual characteristics, ergonomic posture on work fatigue and muscle fatigue/Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) and knowing the impact of bad ergonomic posture on coating pan work (sugar coating) in chocolate meses production PT. X.

Keywords : Ergonomics, Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs), *Rapid Upper Limb Assessment* (RULA), Subjective Symptom Questionnaire (SST), Nordic Body Map (NBM)

Abstrak. Ergonomi memiliki hubungan yang erat dengan karakteristik fungsional manusia, seperti kemampuan penginderaan, respon, daya ingat, posisi optimum tangan dan kaki. Divisi coating pan sendiri merupakan salah satu proses produksi dalam produk cokelat meses. Pegawai pada divisi coating pan melakukan pekerjaan dengan posisi berdiri dengan jam kerja 8 jam/hari dengan waktu 6 (enam) hari dalam 1 (satu) minggu. Gerakan postur janggal merupakan salah satu faktor risiko untuk terjadinya gangguan, penyakit, atau cedera pada sistem muskuloskeletal. Kelelahan merupakan mekanisme perlindungan tubuh agar tubuh menghindari kerusakan lebih lanjut, sehingga terjadi pemulihan. Semua jenis pekerjaan baik formal dan informal menimbulkan kelelahan kerja, dengan menurunkan kinerja dan menambah kesalahan kerja. Faktor ergonomi tidak baik, fisik lingkungan, kondisi fisik responden, kelelahan dan musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) yang mempengaruhi risiko ergonomi pada pegawai coating pan. Karakteristik responden yaitu Usia, berat badan dan tinggi badan mempunyai hubungan kuat dengan kelelahan kerja dan Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSDs)/kelelahan otot. Penilaian tingkat risiko ergonomi menggunakan metode *Rapid Upper Limb Assessment* (RULA) serta Nordic Body Map (NBM). Untuk kelelahan di lakukan pengisian kuesioner *The Subjective Symptom* (SST) dimana kuesioner tersebut berisi 30 pertanyaan mengenai gejala kelelahan kerja. Adapun tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah Mengetahui permasalahan dan tingkat risiko ergonomi dalam pekerjaan coating pan (pelapisan gula) pada cokelat meses PT. X. Mengetahui pengaruh lingkungan fisik, karakteristik individual, postur ergonomi terhadap kelelahan kerja dan kelelahan otot/ Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSDs) serta mengetahui dampak dari postur ergonomi tidak baik pada pekerjaan coating pan (pelapisan gula) pada produksi cokelat meses PT. X.

Kata kunci: Ergonomi, Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs), *Rapid Upper Limb Assessment* (RULA), kuesioner Subjective Symptom (SST), Nordic Body Map (NBM)

1. Introduction

Ergonomics has a close relationship with human functional characteristics, such as sensing ability, response, memory, optimum position of

the hands and feet. Ergonomics is useful in improving human performance in work to interact and reduce injuries in activities that are

safe, comfortable, healthy, efficient and effective (Nurmiyanto, E. 1998). By applying ergonomics, not only benefits workers, but can increase efficiency, increase productivity, reduce lost work time due to illness or injury and can reduce insurance costs (Hasyti, 2019). In the study of ergonomics, there is an adjustment between work and workers, while what happens in general, employees adjust to work. This discrepancy can cause work accidents, illness or fatigue (WHO-EM, 2002).

Ergonomics plays an important role in improving occupational safety and health factors, such as the design of work systems to reduce aches and pains in the human skeletal system and the design of visual aid workplaces. In Indonesia, according to the results of the 2005 Ministry of Health Health Problem Profile survey, about 40.5% of employees' illnesses are related to their work and health problems. This is based on a survey conducted of 482 employees in 12 districts and cities in Indonesia. In addition, according to the same study, the function of the ligaments, muscles, nerves, joints and tendons, and the spine of employees generally experience disturbances (16%).

Awkward posture movements are a risk factor for disorders, diseases, or injuries to the musculoskeletal system (Hummantech, 1995). An awkward posture made by an employee of the coating pan division (sugar coating) at PT. This X can impact stress and affect the physical condition of employees, so that it can cause injury to employees. This is based on employee complaints submitted to management in writing in the 2020-2021 period.

Fatigue shows different conditions for each individual, but all of them lead to loss of efficiency and decreased work capacity and fatigue is a protective mechanism for the body so that the body avoids further damage, resulting in recovery (Umyati, 2010). All types of work, both formal and informal, lead to job burnout. Work fatigue will reduce performance and increase work errors. Decreasing performance means decreasing work productivity. If the level of productivity of a worker is disrupted due to physical and psychological fatigue, then the result will be felt by the company in the form of a decrease in company productivity.

Data from the International Labor Organization (ILO) states that almost every year as many as two million employees die due to work accidents caused by work fatigue. The study stated that out of 58,115 samples, 32.8% or around 18,828 samples suffered from work fatigue.

Almost all company activities depend on the resources of its workers because labor plays an important role in the course of the company's production process (Hasyti, 2019). The level of labor productivity can be influenced by the physical work environment factors. Discomfort at work is a condition that lowers morale and tends to be boring, on the other hand if comfort can be created in the physical work environment then workers can carry out production activities optimally due to comfortable and supportive environmental conditions.

The pan coating division itself is one of the production processes in chocolate meses products. Coating pan work is a semi-manual job where in this work a coating tool is used, but for coating materials it is done manually. Employees in the coating pan division work in a standing position with working hours of 8 hours/day with 6 (six) days in 1 (one) week.

To prevent injury, it is necessary to assess the level of ergonomic risk for employees of the coating pan division (sugar coating) at PT. X. Even though the work process is interspersed with breaks, the condition of working in a standing position coupled with the burden on the hands for a long period of time poses an ergonomic risk. This is because working in a standing position continuously can lead to awkward postures.

Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) are disorders of the skeletal muscles caused by the muscles receiving repetitive and continuous static loads for a long period of time and will cause complaints to the joints, ligaments and tendons. *Musculoskeletal Disorders* (MSDs) are generally in the form of pain, injury, or abnormalities in the musculoskeletal system, including the nerves, tendons, ligaments, muscles or joints. Working with pain can reduce work productivity and if working with pain is continued it will result in disability which ultimately eliminates jobs for workers.

According to Sedarmayanti (2007) states that the adverse effects that can be caused by an unfavorable physical work environment on the health of workers are as follows:

1. Noise, causing dizziness/headaches, feeling nauseous, and shortness of breath
2. Lighting, causes eye fatigue which ultimately results in eye damage
3. Temperature, causing disruption of work performance such as fatigue that comes too early and loss of body fluids or dehydration.

The results of research conducted by PT. Waskita Karya in 2009 on 9,482 employees of the company in 12 districts/cities in Indonesia generally in the form of Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) SDs (16%), cardiovascular (8%), nervous disorders (5%), respiratory disorders (3%) and ENT disorders (1.5%). Based on these data it shows that *Musculoskeletal Disorders* (MSDs) have the highest number as a disorder that is often experienced by workers.

The aim of this research is to find out the ergonomic problems and risk levels in the coating pan work on PT. X. Knowing the effect of the physical environment, individual characteristics, ergonomic posture on work fatigue and Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) and knowing the impact of bad ergonomic posture on coating pan work (sugar coating) in the production of chocolate meses PT. X

2 Methodology

2.1 Research object

The object of this research is all employees in the coating pan division (sugar coating) in the chocolate meses production of PT. X. PT.X is a consumer goods company engaged in food retail business activities. PT.X is located in the city of Bandung, West Java. The food products that are produced are chocolate meses, chocolate blocks, and chocolate filling (Hasyti, 2019). The company started its business in 2004.

2.2. Data type

The data used in this study are primary data and secondary data.

Secondary data, namely:

1. Biodata of employees of the coating pan division (sugar coating) in the production of chocolate meses PT. X.
2. Data on the health of employees of the coating pan division (sugar coating) on the production of chocolate meses at PT. X.
3. A written complaint by an employee of the coating pan division (sugar coating) on the production of chocolate meses at PT. X

Primary data ie

1. Physical work environment (temperature, light and noise)
2. Characteristics of respondents (based on weight, height, age, and length of work in the coating pan division)
3. Rapid Upper Limb Assessment Method (RULA)
4. Nordic Body Map Questionnaire (NBM)
5. The Subjective Symptom Questionnaire (SST)

2.3. Data collection

1. Air temperature

Room temperature data collection is carried out using data from a Digital Thermo-Hygrometer device. The results are the average temperature during research activities.

2. Light

Light data collection is carried out using data from the Lux Light Meter. According to the Decree of the Minister of Health No. 261/MENKES/SK/II/1998 Concerning: Work Environment Health Requirements There are lighting requirements for industrial work environments. There are these requirements which are the recommended lighting level values based on the type of area, work or certain activities. The minimum standard value for lighting for coating pan work is included in Industrial Activities and Handicrafts – Food by Type of Area, Occupation/Activity of the Cooking Process at Preservation Factories and Factories chocolate place and work area in sugar factory i.e. 200 lux. In addition, the minimum number of measurement points is 36 points, the measurement point is the meeting point between the two diagonal lines of the length and width of the room. This is in accordance with SNI 7062: 2019 concerning Measurement of lighting intensity in the workplace. The data obtained

from the Lux Light Meter is then averaged and categorized whether it meets or not.

3. Noise

The collection of noise data uses data from . This tool has produced an Equivalent Continuous Noise Level (Leq) value. After getting Leq every minute, from minute 1 (LI) to minute 10 (LX). Then, proceed with calculating LTM5 and LS. Then the LS value is compared to No. 261/MENKES/SK/II/1998 where the room noise level in the workspace is a maximum of 85 dBA in an average measurement of 8 hours.

4. Nordic body map (NBM)

Completion of questionnaires by employees (gender, age, years of service and level of perceived complaints) in order to obtain the level of *Musculoskeletal Disorders* (MSDs) complaints. The *Nordic Body Map (NBM)* questionnaire has 28 points or questions starting from 0 to 27 point numbers that can be assessed using a Likert scale to see the level of *Musculoskeletal Disorder* (MSDs) complaints objectively. All are presented into three parts, namely the neck, upper limb (shoulders, elbows, hands and wrists), lower limb (hips, thighs, knees, ankles and feet) and low back (upper and lower back) (Andersson et al. , 2007). The measurement results obtained from the *Nordic Body Map (NBM)* questionnaire are classified based on the table below:

Table 1. Classification of risk levels for *musculoskeletal disorders* (MSDs) based on individual total scores

Risk Level	Individual Total Score	Risk Level	Corrective action
1	28-49	Low	No corrective action is required
2	50-70	Currently	Action may be required in the future
3	71-91	Tall	Urgent action is required
4	92-112	Very high	Comprehensive action is needed as soon as possible

Source: Tarwaka, 2013

5. *Rapid upper limb assessment (RULA)*
the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) method uses *the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA)* score to assess body posture. The observation results were compared with the

Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) Employee Assessment Worksheet. If the calculation of the final *Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA)* score has been obtained, it can determine what action must be taken/action level of the working posture. *Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA)* Action Level (Wijaya, ISA, & Muhsin, A., 2018).

Table 2. *Rapid upper limb assessment (RULA)* action level

RULA score	Action levels	risk levels	action
1-2	1	Acceptable	not necessary
3-4	2	Low	May be necessary
5-6	3	high	Necessary as early as possible
7	4	Very hogh	Necessary NOW

Source: Wijaya, ISA, & Muhsin, A., 2018

6. *The subjective symptoms (SST)*

How to assess the level of fatigue is done by scoring the answers to *the Subjective Symptom (SST)* questionnaire where the score is as follows:

1. Value 30-52 = Low level of Fatigue
2. Value 53-75 = Moderate fatigue
3. Value 76-98 = High level of fatigue
4. Value 99-120 = Very high level of fatigue (Tarwaka, 2013)

2.4. Data processing

Data analysis in this research is using quantitative data which is done descriptively. The data analysis technique has the goal of describing good ergonomics attitudes, work fatigue, physical environment, muscle fatigue in doing Manual Material Handling work and categorizing fatigue levels after carrying out work activities. This analysis displays the results of calculating each variable, then the analysis used is Spearman's correlation analysis which has the goal of knowing the relationship between variables. In addition, Linear Regression Test analysis was carried out to obtain the relationship between work fatigue and muscle fatigue with factors that have the potential to cause work fatigue in the coating pan division (sugar coating) in PT. X . The factors are work environment (temperature, noise and lighting), characteristics of

respondents (age, height, weight, length of work, age and smoking) and posture ergonomics.

3 Results and discussion

3.1. Characteristics of respondents

a. Age

The results of field data show that the highest number of respondents is in the age range of 36-40 years, namely 50% or 12 people, 30-35 years 33% and 41-45 years equals 20%.

Figure 1. Age of respondent

b. Height

For height the highest number of respondents had height in the range of 165-169 cm the number of respondents was 21 people (87.5%).

Figure 2. Respondent's height

c. Weight

The results of field data for weight characteristics, the largest number of respondents have weight in the range of 60-70 kg the number of respondents is 21 people (87.5%).

Figure 3. Respondent's weight

d. Working period in coating oan division

the respondent's working period is 9 years with 8 respondents (37.5%) and the lowest number is 10 years with 4 respondents (16.77%).

Figure 4. Working period in the coating pan division

e. Shift work

From the results of the questionnaire data, it was stated that the number of respondents with the afternoon shift had the highest number, namely 54.17% and for the afternoon shift, 45.83%.

Figure 5. Shift work in the coating pan division

f. Smoke

Smoking activities by workers get numbers, namely 62.5% of respondents who do not smoke have the highest rate and only 37.5% do smoking activities.

Figure 6. Snoring respondent

3.2. Physical work environment

a. working room temperature with a range of 19°C based on regulation NO.261/MENKES/SK/II/1998, is still categorized as safe. Due to this regulation the room temperature ranges from 18°C-26°C

b. Lighting is still in the safe category, which is vulnerable to 185-189 lux, this is based on Permenaker number 5 of 2018 where the minimum limit is 100 Lux and the maximum is 200 lux, namely for Industry and Craft - Food activities with Types of Area, Occupation/Activity The cooking process in

pickling and chocolate factory place and work area in sugar factory.

c. Noise based on regulation NO.261/MENKES/SK/II/1998, the room noise level in the workspace is a maximum of 85 dBA in an average measurement of 8 hours. For the pan coating room, the noise is at 81.06 dB and the highest is 82.96 dB, so it is still in the range below the maximum value.

3.3. Risk of work posture using *the rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) method*

In the Coating pan process there are several measurements that will be carried out such as risks in work related to upper limb disorders, identifying the effort needed by muscles related to body posture at work (repetitive use of force and static work) (McAtamney, et al., 1993). The results of the measurement of work posture risk show that 92% of respondents have a high level of risk with the results of the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) 5-6 and 8% of respondents have a very high level of risk with the results of the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) 7 .

Figure 7. Evaluation results of the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) method

3.4. Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) / muscle fatigue using *the nordic body map (NBM) method*

Filling in muscle fatigue with the Nordic Body Map (NBM) method obtained the level of complaints. Assessment of Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSDs) complaints using the Nordic Body Map (NBM) method 88% of the respondents had a high level of fatigue with a value range of 71-91 and 12% of the respondents had a moderate level of fatigue with a value range of 50-70.

Figure 8. Evaluation results of the nordic body map (NBM) method

3.5. Work fatigue with *the subjective symptom (SST) questionnaire method*

Measurement of work fatigue was measured by The Subjective Symptom (SST) questionnaire. Work fatigue assessment was measured by The Subjective Symptom Questionnaire (SST) to get the result that 63% of the respondents were moderate fatigue with a value range of 53-75 and 37% had high fatigue with a value range of 76-98.

Figure 9. Evaluation results of the subjective symptom (SST) questionnaire method

3.6. Relationship between physical environment, response characteristics and ergonomic postures with work fatigue

The physical environment, in this case noise, has a Sig value. (2-tailed) $0.001 <$ smaller than 0.05, it means that there is a significant (significant) relationship and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is 0.641 or strong. For temperature and lighting have no relationship with work fatigue where each Sig. (2-tailed) temperature 0.81 and lighting 0.396 all $>$ from 0.05. For the strength of the relationship, it is weak for lighting with a value of 0.182, while for temperature it is less significant with a value of 0.052

For the characteristics of the respondent (Smoking) it has a Sig value. (2-tailed) $0.01 <$ smaller than 0.05 on work fatigue so that it means there is a significant relationship (significant) and the level of strength of the

relationship (correlation) is 0.65 or strong. Working time has a value of Sig. (2-tailed) 0.007 < smaller than 0.05, it means that there is a significant (significant) relationship and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is 0.536 or strong. As for the characteristics of the respondents (height and weight) have a significant relationship (mean) with the value of Sig. (2-tailed) height 0.016 and Sig. (2-tailed) body weight 0.015 < less than 0.05 means there is a significant (significant) relationship, and the level of correlation strength (correlation) is moderate with values for height of 0.488 and body weight of 0.489. The strength of the relationship is less significant, namely age with a value of 0.089.

Likewise, ergonomic posture has a value of Sig. (2-tailed) 0.002 < smaller than 0.05, it means that there is a significant (significant) relationship and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is 0.597 or strong.

3.7. Relationship between physical environment, response characteristics and ergonomic postures with muscle fatigue/musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs)

The physical environment, in this case noise, has a Sig value. (2-tailed) 0.013 < smaller than 0.05, it means that there is a significant (significant) relationship and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is 0.501 or strong. For temperature and lighting have no relationship with muscle fatigue where each value is Sig. (2-tailed) temperature 0.79 and lighting 0.5 all > from 0.05. For the strength of the relationship, it is weak for lighting with a value of 0.145, while for temperature it is less significant with a value of 0.057 for temperature .

For the characteristics of the respondent (Smoking) it has a Sig value. (2-tailed) 0.01 < smaller than 0.05 on work fatigue so that it means there is a significant relationship (significant) and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is 0.643 or strong. Working time has a value of Sig. (2-tailed) 0.012 < smaller than 0.05, it means that there is a significant (significant) relationship and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is 0.502 or strong. As for the characteristics of

the respondents (height and weight) have a significant relationship (mean) with the value of Sig. (2-tailed) height 0.029 and Sig. (2-tailed) body weight 0.019 < smaller than 0.05, it means that there is a significant (significant) relationship, and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is moderate with values for height of 0.474 and body weight of 0.474. For the age value of Sig. (2-tailed) 0.75 > 0.05 so that it has no relationship with muscle fatigue and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is 0.068 or less significant.

Ergonomics posture has a value of Sig. (2-tailed) 0.02 < smaller than 0.05, it means that there is a significant (significant) relationship and the level of strength of the relationship (correlation) is 0.609 or strong.

3. 8. Relation of physical environment, respondent characteristics and ergonomic posture to work fatigue

The results of the linear regression test stated that: Work environment (Temperature, noise and lighting), Respondent characteristics (Age, Height, Weight, Length of Work, age and smoking) on work fatigue obtained a determination (R square) of 0.875, presentation of influence given by the independent variable is equal to 87.5%. While the remaining 12.5% is influenced by other variables that are not included in this research model. Sig. Value (2-tailed) 0.001 (p <0.05) means that there is an influence between the independent variables on work fatigue. In addition, the following equation is obtained which is used to find the probability of work fatigue occurring.

$$Y = -402.756 + 0.956X_1 + 2.724X_2 + 0.275X_3 + 2.831X_4 + 1.121X_5 + 0.229X_6 + 8.587X_7 + 0.136X_8 - 1.173X_9 \quad (1)$$

With

Y = Muscle fatigue

X₁ = Lighting

X₂ = Temperature

X₃ = Noise

X₄ = Ergonomic posture

X₅ = Height

X₆ = body weight

X₇ = Smoking
 X₈ = Age
 X₉ = Working time

The magnitude of the probability of burnout can be found by the equation above. Below is an example of the calculation:

For example

Respondent data 1

X ₁ (Lighting)	=	189
X ₂ (Temperature)	=	19
X ₃ (Noise)	=	82
X ₄ (ergonomics posture)	=	7
X ₅ (Height)	=	170
X ₆ (Weight)	=	73
X ₇ (Smoke)	=	2
X ₈ (Age)	=	39
X ₉ (Years of service)	=	10

$$Y = -402.756 + 0.956X_1 + 2.724X_2 + 0.275X_3 + 2.831X_4 + 1.121X_5 + 0.229X_6 + 8.587X_7 + 0.136X_8 - 1.173X_9$$

$$Y = -402.756 + 180.684 + 51.756 + 22.55 + 19.817 + 190.57 + 16.717 + 17.174 + 5.304 - 11.73$$

$$Y = 90.1$$

According to the classification of the level of work fatigue (Tarwaka, 2013) the value of Y = 90.1 is in the range of values 76-98, which is a high level of fatigue. This category is the same as the results of the questionnaire using the Subjective Symptom (SST) questionnaire for respondent 1 with a score of 85 which includes the high fatigue category.

3.9. Relationship between physical environment, respondent characteristics and ergonomic postures on work muscle fatigue/ musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs).

The results of the linear regression test stated that: work environment (temperature, noise and lighting), Respondent characteristics (age, height, weight, length of work, age and smoking) on muscle fatigue Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSDs) obtained a determination (R square) of 0.814, the presentation of the contribution of influence given by the independent variable is 81.4%. While the remaining 18.6% is influenced by other variables that are not included in this research model. Sig. Value (2-tailed) 0.001 (p < 0.05)

means that there is an influence between the independent variables on work fatigue. In addition, the following equation is obtained which is used to find the probability of Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSDs) muscle fatigue

$$Y = -487.744 + 0.839X_1 + 2.882X_2 + 1.561X_3 + 1.216X_4 + 1.011X_5 + 0.433X_6 + 9.792X_7 + 0.209X_8 - 0.873X_9 \quad (2)$$

With

Y = work fatigue

X₁ = Exposure

X₂ = Temperature

X₃ = Noise

X₄ = Ergonomic posture

X₅ = Height

X₆ = Weight

X₇ = Smoking

X₈ = Age

X₉ = Working time

The magnitude of the probability of muscle fatigue / Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) can be found by the above equation. Below is an example of the calculation:

For example

Respondent data 1

X ₁ (Lighting)	=	189
X ₂ (Temperature)	=	19
X ₃ (Noise)	=	82
X ₄ (ergonomics posture)	=	7
X ₅ (Height)	=	170
X ₆ (Weight)	=	73
X ₇ (Smoke)	=	2
X ₈ (Age)	=	39
X ₉ (Years of service)	=	10

$$Y = -487.744 + 0.839X_1 + 2.882X_2 + 1.561X_3 + 1.216X_4 + 1.011X_5 + 0.433X_6 + 9.792X_7 + 0.209X_8 - 0.873X_9$$

$$Y = -472,949 + 132,111 + 60,344 + 124,722 + 9,016 + 183.6 + 22,192 + 17,586 + 7,956 - 8.73$$

$$Y = 76.5$$

According to the classification of Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) (Tarwaka, 2013) the value of Y = 76.5 is in the range of values 71-91, namely high levels of fatigue. This category is the same as the results of the Nordic Body Map (NBM) method where

respondent 1 has a score of 90 which is included in the high fatigue category.

4 Conclusion

The current physical work environment, such as the temperature in the work room with a range of 19 ° C according to MENKES NO.261/MENKES/SK/II/1998, is still categorized as safe. Due to these regulations the room temperature ranges from 18°C-26°C. Lighting is still in a safe category, which is vulnerable to 185-189 lux, this is based on Permenaker number 5 of 2018 where the minimum limit is 100 Lux and the maximum is 200 lux. For noise it is still within limits, namely the lowest is 81.06 dB and the highest is 82.96 dB. The quality standard for industrial room noise levels according to regulation NO.261/MENKES/SK/II/1998 is a maximum of 85 dBA in an average measurement of 8 hours.

The characteristics of the respondents in this study were 50% in the age range of 36-40 years. or as many as 12 people, 30-35 years 33% and 41-45 years at 20%. For the height of the most respondents in the range 165-169 cm the number of respondents was 21 people (87.5%). Most respondents' body weight has a body weight in the range of 60-70 kg the number of respondents is 21 people (87.5%). The length of work in the pan coating division was 8 respondents (37.5%) with 9 years of service. The afternoon shift had the highest rate, namely 54.17% and for the afternoon shift, 45.83%. Non-smokers had the highest rate, namely 62.5% and only 37.5% smoked.

Ergonomic posture risk assessment using the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) method yielded the result that 92% of respondents had a high level of risk with the results of the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) 5-6 and 8% of respondents had a very high risk level with the results of the assessment Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) 7.

Assessment of Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSDs) complaints using the Nordic Body Map (NBM) method 88% of the respondents had a high level of fatigue with a value range of 71-91 and 12% of the respondents had a moderate level of fatigue with a value range of 50-70.

Work fatigue assessment was measured by The Subjective Symptom Questionnaire (SST) to get the result that 63% of the respondents were moderate fatigue with a value range of 53-75 and 37% had high fatigue with a value range of 76-98.

Reference

1. Abeysekera, J. 2002. Ergonomic and Industrially Developing Countries. Indonesian Journal of Ergonomics, Vol. 1(1):3-12
2. Anies. 2005. Occupational Diseases. First Print. PT. Elex Media Komputindo. Jakarta
3. Ayu Bidiawati JR*, Eva Suryani. (2015): Improving The Work Position of Worker's Based on Quick Exposure Check Method to Reduce the Risk of Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders, Procedia Manufacturing 4 (2015) 496 – 503, obtained via internet site: www.sciencedirect.com
4. AZ/NZS 4360:1999. 1999. The Australian Standard/New Zealand 4360:1999. Risk Management Guidelines. Sydney. Australia
5. Briansah AO. Analysis of work postures that occur for activities in building construction projects using the Rula method at CV. Basani. 2018;1–70. Available from: <https://dspace.uui.ac.id/handle/123456789/11895>
6. Cornell University. 2004. Arranging Your Workstation Economically. Available from URL: <http://www.Google.Com/CUergoweb/posturetyping.html>[Accessed: December 17, 2021]
7. Darlis, et al. 2009. Ergonomic Considerations in Work Station Design. Sigma Epsilon, vol 13(4): 105-110
8. RI Ministry of Health, RI Ministry of Health. 2007. Indonesian Health Profile 2005. Jakarta: Indonesian Ministry of Health 2005.
9. Enggaela, D, et al. 2013. Work Posture Analysis of Sugar Transportation Workers in Storage Warehouses Using the Ovako Work Posture Analysis System Method. Engineering Journal. (on line). Accessed from :

- <http://kriptipftp.staff.ub.ac.id/files/2015/03/9.-JURNAL-Dyah-Intani-Enggaela.pdf>
10. HSE, Health Safety Executive. 2007. Understanding ergonomics at work – Reduce accidents and ill health and increase productivity by fitting the task to the worker – Health and Safety Executive.
 11. Indah Rachmatiah Siti Salami, et al. 2015. Occupational Safety and Health. First printing. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
 12. ILO. 2013. The Prevention of Occupational Diseases [Online]. Available: www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/wcms_204755.pdf
 13. O. Kaewboonchoo, et al. “The Standardized Nordic Questionnaire Applied to Workers Exposed to Hand-Arm Vibration” Journal of Occupational Health. Vol 40. 1998. pp 218-222
 14. Qomariyatus Sholihaha*, Aprizal Satria Hanafib, Ahmad Alim Bachric, Rahmi Fauziad (2-15): Ergonomics Awareness as Efforts to Increase Knowledge and Prevention of Musculoskeletal Disorders on Fishermen, Industrial Engineering and Service Science 2015, obtained through the internet site: www.sciencedirect.com
 15. Rachman. 2008. Comparative Analysis of Pedicab Driver Complaints Using the Nordic Questionnaire. thesis. Gundharma University. Depok
 16. Rino Andias Anugraha*, Wiyono Sutan, Ilma Mufidah (2015): The design of batik stamp tool scraping working table using ergonomics principles, Industrial Engineering and Service Science 2015, obtained through the internet site: www.sciencedirect.com
 17. Riyadina, Woro. 2008. Musculoskeletal Pain among Industrial Workers in Pulo Gadung Industrial Estate, Jakarta. Indonesian Doctors Association
 18. Santoso, G. 2004. Ergonomics of Humans, Equipment and the Environment. Jakarta: Publisher Library Achievements
 19. Syukri Sahab, 1997. Occupational Safety and Health Management Techniques. Jakarta: PT Bina Resources Human Resources.
 20. Suma'mur. 1996. Ergonomics for Work Productivity. Jakarta: Swabhawa Karya Foundation
 21. Tarwaka. 2011. Industrial Ergonomics, Fundamentals of Ergonomic Knowledge and Applications in the Workplace Ed 1, Cet. 2. Surakarta: Hope Press.

References

- Hasyti, Y. (2019, November). Benefits of Monitoring & Measuring OHS Performance in Work Activities. *GEOPLANART*, 57-61. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.35138/gp.v2i1.135>

22.